

Fermat's last theorem final.

The reason why $G = R + L$
is impossible.

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Abstract

Until

1. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15793350>

2. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17181860>

We derived that in FLT,

$$(X, Y, Z) = \left(\frac{G^n - R^n + L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + R^n - L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + R^n + L^n}{2} \right) \quad (\theta)$$

and

$$G = R + L$$

Now, we will finally prove why $G = R + L$ is impossible and show that Fermat's last theorem is true.

In (θ), multiply 2 and substitute $G = R + L$, then

$$\begin{aligned} & \{(R + L)^n - R^n + L^n\}^n + \{(R + L)^n + R^n - L^n\}^n \\ & = \{(R + L)^n + R^n + L^n\}^n \end{aligned}$$

Let's find the common part in the equation.

$$\begin{aligned} & (R + L)^n - R^n - L^n \\ & = \binom{n}{1} R^{n-1} L + \binom{n}{2} R^{n-2} L^2 + \dots \\ & + \binom{n}{n-2} R^2 L^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1} R L^{n-1} \end{aligned}$$

Let this part as Ψ .

That is,

$$(R + L)^n - R^n - L^n = \Psi$$

$$(R + L)^n = \Psi + R^n + L^n$$

Therefore, the equation is

$$(\Psi + 2L^n)^n + (\Psi + 2R^n)^n = (\Psi + 2R^n + 2L^n)^n$$

Let's focus on $(\Psi + 2R^n + 2L^n)^n$.

$$\begin{aligned}
& (\Psi + 2R^n + 2L^n)^n \\
&= (\Psi + 2R^n + 2L^n) \times (\Psi + 2R^n + 2L^n) \times \dots \\
&\times (\Psi + 2R^n + 2L^n) \quad (\vartheta)
\end{aligned}$$

(n times product)

And the results of this n-times product can be classified into the following three categories.

- 1) Only Ψ and $2R^n$ are mixed (ignore $2L^n$)
- 2) Only Ψ and $2L^n$ are mixed (ignore $2R^n$)
- 3) Contains at least one of term $2R^n$ and $2L^n$.

Think about 1).

The result of 1) is same as $X^n = (\Psi + 2R^n)^n$.

The result of 2) is same as $Y^n = (\Psi + 2L^n)^n$.

So 1) and 2) is canceled by left-hand side.

But terms from 3) are still remaining and it is not zero.

Therefore it is contradiction.

Equation (ϑ) is impossible. [Lemma1019]

Therefore, Fermat's last theorem - for the case $n \nmid XYZ$ has no natural number solution.

How about the case $n \mid XYZ$?

Since X, Y, Z are coprime each other, only one of them can be a multiple of n .

In summary, if X or Y is a multiple of n , (X, Y, Z) must satisfy following form.

$$(X, Y, Z) = \left(\frac{G^n - n^{kn-1}R^n + L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + n^{kn-1}R^n - L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + n^{kn-1}R^n + L^n}{2} \right)$$

I already proved it last time.

It can prove more easily that why natural number ordered pair is impossible.

Remember n is fixed constant and focus on polynomial structure by multiple identity theorem.

Last, the case $n \mid Z$.

Actually it is almost same as form (θ) .

$$(X, Y, Z) = \left(\frac{n^{kn}G^n - R^n + L^n}{2}, \frac{n^{kn}G^n + R^n - L^n}{2}, \frac{n^{kn}G^n + R^n + L^n}{2} \right)$$

$$n^k G \mid (R^n + L^n)$$

n is constant. So if we substitute $(G, R, L) = (2G, 2R, 2L)$, n does not change!!

$$G = aR + bL$$

$$R^n + L^n = n^k(aR + bL) \times f(R, L)$$

$f(R, L)$ cannot be factored out maintaining multiple identity.

By the multiple identity theorem, $f(R, L)$ must satisfy the form:

$$f(R, L) = c_1 R^{n-1} + c_2 R^{n-2}L + \dots + c_{n-1} RL^{n-2} + c_n L^{n-1}$$

Since the coefficient of R^n is 1,

$$n^k a c_1 R^n = R^n$$

$$n^k a c_1 = 1$$

$$c_1 = \frac{1}{n^k a}$$

And the coefficient of L^n is 1.

$$n^k b c_n L^n = L^n$$

$$n^k b c_n = 1$$

$$c_n = \frac{1}{n^k b}$$

And the other coefficients are all zero.

$$R^{n-1}L, R^{n-2}L^2, \dots, R^2L^{n-2}, RL^{n-1}$$

$$n^k a c_2 R^{n-1}L + n^k b c_1 R^{n-1}L = 0$$

$$a c_2 + b c_1 = 0$$

Since $c_1 = \frac{1}{n^k a}$,

$$a c_2 + b \frac{1}{n^k a} = 0 \quad (\chi 1)$$

$$n^k b c_{n-1} R L^{n-1} + n^k a c_n R L^{n-1} = 0$$

$$b c_{n-1} + a c_n = 0$$

Since $c_n = \frac{1}{n^k b}$,

$$b c_{n-1} + a \frac{1}{n^k b} = 0 \quad (\chi 2)$$

Focus on $(\chi_1), (\chi_2)$

$$ac_2 + b \frac{1}{n^k a} = 0$$

$$a^2 n^k c_2 + b = 0 \quad (\chi_3)$$

Since a, b are natural numbers,

$$\therefore b|a$$

$$bc_{n-1} + a \frac{1}{n^k b} = 0$$

$$b^2 n^k c_{n-1} + a = 0 \quad (\chi_4)$$

$$\therefore a|b$$

$b|a$ and $a|b$ means that $a = b$.

Therefore, in (χ_3) ,

$$a^2 n^k c_2 + a = 0$$

$$c_2 = -\frac{1}{an^k}$$

in (χ_4) ,

$$a^2 n^k c_{n-1} + a = 0$$

$$c_{n-1} = -\frac{1}{n^k a}$$

$$\therefore c_1 = c_{n-1} = -c_1 = -c_n$$

Repeat this process, we get decomposition that we already knows,

$$\begin{aligned} R^n + L^n &= n^k(aR + aL) \\ &\times \left\{ \frac{1}{n^k a} R^{n-1} - \frac{1}{n^k a} R^{n-1}L + \dots - \frac{1}{n^k a} RL^{n-1} + \frac{1}{n^k a} L^n \right\} \\ &= (R + L)\{R^{n-1} - R^{n-2}L + \dots - RL^{n-1} + L^n\} \end{aligned}$$

And this form is impossible by [Lemma1019]

As a result,

$$X^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

in this equation, there is no natural number ordered pair (X, Y, Z) that satisfy this equation.

Therefore, Fermat's last theorem is true.